

Communication Strategy Plan for the OSPARK Project

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This project is all about teaching communication and marketing skills to people who want to make their Open Science initiatives, services or infrastructures more known. This communication strategy plan lays out how to reach those people in order to help them achieve their goal.

Audience Analysis

Our target audience for communication are people who lead or communicate about Open Science initiatives, services or infrastructures. Since this project is part of OSCARS, we want to target specifically initiatives, services and infrastructures which are part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Furthermore, our own initiatives have community members, who would benefit from learning the tools and strategies we build as part of OSPARK–DRA trainers and OLS community members.

As our training is about communication, our target audience has their own target audience to whom they want to communicate. Hence, this plan also serves as an example for their endeavours.

We further split up the communicator of Open Science initiative/service/infrastructure into internal and external communicators to reflect different needs and goals in this broad audience.

Needs, preferences, and behaviours of our audience

Audience type	Needs	Preferences	Behaviours
Internal communicator of Open Science	Seeing open science practices adopted or expanded within their	University staff are often time constrained, so short and accessible content may	University staff often attend conferences and seminars (both research and

	<p>institution/organisation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Getting management "buy in" (for example, to implement services institutionally, to build time for OS into work plans, to train staff and students, or to provide incentives for OS practices within the institution). - Increasing grassroots support among students and academics. - Acquiring funding to train in, pilot, or implement new open science practices. - Recognition for their internal OS advocacy. - Meeting their professional development requirements. 	<p>be preferred.</p> <p>They also need information which holds academic social currency, so information should reference or be published in academic journal articles.</p> <p>Writing should be formal but easy to process.</p> <p>Meetings should be accessible (online or hybrid, using accessibility tools) and as short as possible.</p>	<p>professional services focused).</p> <p>Many students and university staff are active on LinkedIn, TikTok, BlueSky, or Mastodon professionally.</p> <p>University staff regularly use email lists.</p> <p>University staff can have limited decision-making regarding spending.</p> <p>Most researchers at universities in high income countries (HICs) will have access to training/professional development funds which can be used at their discretion. Professional services departments may also have pots of money for this.</p>
<p>External communicator of Open Science initiative, service, or infrastructure</p> <p>Note: Many of these communicators are also university staff or students, so have the same needs, preferences and behaviours as internal communicators.</p>	<p>Increasing awareness of and engagement with their Open Science initiative:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reaching researchers, professionals, managers and the public beyond the open science "bubble". - Acquiring funding to develop or expand their Open Science initiative. - Getting formal recognition for their Open Science initiative. - Increasing researchers' use of their Open Science initiative within the 	<p>See above.</p>	<p>Open Science initiatives are often working on a very limited budget. Communicators are likely to want value for money.</p> <p>Most Open Science initiatives are active on X (formerly Twitter), BlueSky, or Mastodon. Some also use Instagram or YouTube regularly.</p>

	<p>relevant research field(s).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Getting “buy in” from organisational and institutional leaders across multiple sectors, to facilitate widespread adoption of the Open Science initiative. - Communicating their Open Science initiative efficiently, due to time and funding constraints. 		
<p>DRA Trainer</p>	<p>Feeling seen by the DRA team and getting booked for training.</p> <p>Feeling part of the solution in research (e.g. the reproducibility crisis).</p> <p>Having a sense of belonging to the DRA trainer community.</p> <p>Setting up peer-reviewed training which has been verified by other experts.</p>	<p>Informal communication on Mattermost or email.</p> <p>Time efficient.</p> <p>Information should come in quickly digestible form or—if longer—should be highly relevant for them.</p>	<p>Diverse engagement habits (some interact with Mattermost more often than others).</p>
<p>OLS Mentee</p>	<p>Developing their Open Science skills and practices in ways which are relevant to their circumstances (for example, in line with their cultural requirements).</p> <p>Connecting with and getting peer support from others in the OLS community.</p> <p>Creating visibility for their own open science projects.</p>	<p>OLS mentees are diverse and globally distributed, so content should be online and use accessibility tools.</p> <p>Communication is generally through Slack, email, or Zoom calls.</p> <p>The OLS community has a strong preference for FAIR and ethical tools/channels.</p>	<p>Many OLS community members are based in LMICs, so have very limited funding and may have restricted access to purchasing platforms.</p> <p>OLS community members tend to use social media platforms which are open source/non-profit (such as Mastodon) or professionally oriented (such as LinkedIn).</p>

Where our audience can be reached (Communication Channels)

Audience type	Reachable via
<p>Internal communicator of Open Science</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conferences, seminars, and other events. - Social media. - Email lists.
<p>External communicator of Open Science initiative, service, or infrastructure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conferences, seminars, and other events. - Social media. - Email lists.
<p>DRA Trainer</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mattermost. - Email.
<p>OLS Mentee</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slack. - Email. - Open source or non-profit social media platforms, such as Mastodon. - Professional social media platforms, such as LinkedIn.

Message Development

Project goals and objectives

Our messages should align with the project goals and objectives.

1. Ensure that open science knowledge and tools are FAIR and reach the intended target audience, increasing efficiency and effectiveness of research by facilitating re-use and collaboration on existing resources.
2. Provide opportunities for open science advocates to discover, discuss, practice, and utilise evidence-based marketing, communications and outreach, including formats beyond the scientific paper.

3. Highlight examples of good marketing and communications practice by open science initiatives, services and infrastructures.

Tone, language and content of the messages

Tone

- **Engaging and relatable:** Communicates in an accessible and dynamic way.
- **Conversational and playful yet credible:** Balances a friendly, fun, and informal approach with scientific accuracy and professionalism.
- **Curious and encouraging:** Inspires dialogue, curiosity, and participation.
- **Trustworthy and transparent:** Prioritizes evidence-based information, openness, and clear sourcing.
- **Empowering and inclusive:** Encourages diverse perspectives and makes marketing feel accessible to all.

Language

- **Plain, accessible, and inclusive:** Avoids technical jargon unless necessary, always explaining key terms. Screen-reader friendly, such as through the use of alt text on images.
- **Visual and story-driven:** Uses metaphors, real-world examples, and engaging visuals to clarify abstract concepts.
- **Youthful but respectful:** Strikes a balance between being modern, energetic, and authoritative.
- **Clear and actionable:** Focuses on practical steps Open Science advocates can take to increase their impact.

Content of Messages

- **Visibility & marketing tips:** Practical strategies for scientists to share their work and engage wider audiences.
- **Success stories & case studies:** Highlighting Open Science initiatives and their real-world impact.
- **Community-driven content:** Answering audience questions, featuring interviews, and sharing best practices.

By keeping the messaging **engaging, evidence-based, and actionable**, we ensure that Open Science advocates not only understand the importance of visibility and marketing but feel inspired and equipped to implement it effectively.

Channel Selection and Implementation

For example, email, websites, traditional media, events, or direct mail. The chosen channels should be appropriate for the audience and the message.

Note: Reuse material! You can repost on social media every 6-12 months. People generally do not notice repetition on these timescales.

Target audience: Communicator of Open Science initiative, service, or infrastructure

Tt Type	Tt Description	Tt Outlet	Examples
Short form videos	30-60 second videos which summarise core concepts from the OSPARK bootcamp (for example, "how to record a podcast").	YouTube.	"Scientists love this simple thing" by Psydere. "The summary in every research paper" by Psydere. "#OpenScience Festival #OSF2023DE The future of Open Science" by ZB MED.
Infographics	Graphics which summarise core OSPARK concepts and highlight examples of good communications practice by Open Science initiatives.	Mastodon, LinkedIn, Bluesky.	Neurodiversity by FORRT. "What is ADHD and how does it affect you?" by FORRT. Neurodiversity Pride Day and LGBTQIA+ Pride Month by FORRT.
Podcast (interview)	Reach out to podcasters to see if we can come on their podcast. Format depends on the podcast.	Podcast platforms such as Spotify.	"Digital Research Academy - A Grassroots Network for Trainers" on Code for Thought. "Open Source and Open Science: A Sneak Peak into Research Software Engineering with Deborah Udoh" on the Open Source Education Podcast.
Fact-Sheets	Short (maximum 4 pages) information sheets which summarise core concepts in the OSPARK bootcamp. Note: this would need supporting communications, such as social media	Preprint server. Newsletter.	"Policy brief: Equitable and Inclusive Team Science" by OLS.

Tt Type	Tt Description	Tt Outlet	Examples
	posts.		
Newsletter	Information on upcoming training and opportunities, as well as new and existing content.	Kit .	OSPARK newsletter by DRA .

Target audience: DRA trainers

Tt Type	Tt Description	Tt Outlet	Examples
Information messages	Information on upcoming training, new and existing content and opportunities. Potentially mixed with links to public posts (see table above).	DRA's Mattermost and/or e-mail.	N/A

Target audience: OLS community (including mentees)

Tt Type	Tt Description	Tt Outlet	Examples
Internal team comms	Progress updates for the OLS team, so they're aware of what the OSPARK project is doing.	OLS's internal Slack channels.	N/A
Community-wide comms	Messages and resources to be shared with the OLS community, such as fact sheets, dates for courses.	OLS's general Slack channels. OLS's blog.	N/A
Social media	Messages and resources to be shared with the OLS community. Can also be used to cross-post communications from other channels	OLS's LinkedIn page. OLS's newsletter.	A post on OLS's LinkedIn page .

Tt Type	Tt Description	Tt Outlet	Examples
	(such as shorts, infographics).		

Success evaluation

Criterion	✨ Aspiration ✨
Reach: Number of people who viewed the posts (DRA and OLS LinkedIn pages), messages (OLS Slack or DRA Mattermost), and emails (OSPARK newsletter).	Posts: 300 impressions. Messages: <i>No analytics are available.</i> Emails: 100 subscribers.
Engagement: Number of people who interacted with the posts, messages, and emails.	Posts: 2.5%. Messages: 10 emoji reactions and/or replies. Emails: 60% open rate.
Conversion: Number of sign-ups to the trainings and bootcamps.	35 people per email course. 10 people per training. 12 people per bootcamp.

Crisis communication strategy

Crisis	Strategy
Backlash, for example, to published materials.	Strategy is adjusted, depending on the circumstances. (Unfounded) attacks about the content: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not respond. - Potentially adapt material in the next iteration to avoid future attacks. Personal attacks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not respond. - Support each other and create perspective.

	<p>Legitimate feedback:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respond, but do not react to unkind comments. - Adapt material based on feedback.
Fallout within the team.	<p>Externally: do not discuss this publicly, in-person or online.</p> <p>Internally: follow agreed conflict resolution strategies (see the internal meeting notes and OSPARK Project Management Handbook for details).</p>
Funding becomes uncertain.	<p>Do not share anything about this on public channels, as doing this before a decision is made could influence the decision.</p> <p>Reach out to individuals who may be able to help and have one-to-one conversations, to prepare for if the funding gets pulled.</p> <p>Communicate internally (such as via email or Slack) about the uncertainty.</p>
Funding gets pulled.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate about the situation publicly. - Share problems that arise through the situation. - Ask people for support and ideas on how to proceed.
Information turns out to be unreliable, for example, due to retractions.	<p>Honesty is the best policy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make a clear statement which says what is wrong and what the correct information is. - Update materials to contain the correct information ASAP. - Where possible, add a highly visible signpost (e.g. a red box on a website).
Code of Conduct violations.	<p>For each event it should be clear which organisation is responsible (DRA or OLS). The respective Code of Conduct applies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DRA Code of Conduct - OLS Code of Conduct <p>If people go public with allegations of Code of Conduct breaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact the person and make them feel heard. Additionally, ask them to temporarily hold further public statements until investigations are complete. - Publish a public statement that investigations are being conducted according to the Code of Conduct.